

6-SHO‘BA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI SOHASI UCHUN KADRLAR

ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation. Electronic educational resources (EER) today are an integral part of the educational process and can be used to achieve a variety of learning goals. To study new educational material and gain new knowledge; to develop skills and abilities; to prepare for competitions, olympiads, intellectual tournaments; for testing as a form of control and self-control; for the implementation of distance learning, etc. The importance of EER in the modern educational process of the school is repeatedly emphasized by both the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard of the IEO and the VEP of the IEO. Thus, the use of ESM in the educational process of elementary school is today not just an opportunity, but a requirement for participants in the educational process.

Basic word, phrases: Multimedia technology, software, computer and document camera, other multimedia resources.

Electronic educational resources are educational materials for the reproduction of which electronic devices are used. Currently, schools are provided with modern computers, interactive equipment, electronic resources, access to the Internet. This contributes to the introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process of the school. Computer learning technologies are the process of preparing and transmitting information to the student, the means of implementation of which is a computer. As practice shows, it is already impossible to imagine a modern school without new information technologies. [1].

The main purpose of using ICT is to improve the quality of education.

With the help of computer technology, the following tasks can be solved:

- increasing the intensity of the lesson;
- increasing the motivation of students;
- monitoring their achievements. . [3].

Proper use of the possibilities of modern information technologies in primary school contributes to:

1. Activation of cognitive activity, improving the quality of schoolchildren;
2. Achieving learning goals with the help of modern electronic learning materials intended for use in primary school lessons;
3. Development of self-education and self-control skills in younger students; increasing the level of learning comfort;
4. Reduction of didactic difficulties for students;
5. Increasing the activity and initiative of younger students in the classroom; the development of information thinking of schoolchildren, the formation of information and communication competence;
6. Creating a situation of success.

The most effective electronic educational resources are multimedia resources. In them, learning objects are presented in many different ways: using text, graphics, photos, video, sound and animation. Thus, all kinds of perception are used; consequently, the basis of thinking and practical activity of the child is laid. Multimedia resources do not replace teachers and textbooks, but at the same time create fundamentally new opportunities for mastering the material. [3].

lesson. In addition, fragments of lessons that use presentations reflect one of the main principles of creating a modern lesson - the principle of attractiveness. Thanks to presentations, children who are usually not very active in the classroom begin to actively express their opinions and reason.

Multimedia presentations are a convenient and effective way of presenting information using computer programs. It combines dynamics, sound and image, i.e. those factors that hold the child's attention for the longest time.

Each EMC is designed to assist in the study and systematization of theoretical knowledge, the formation of practical skills in both the subject area and in the system of distance education or in the traditional educational system using information technology [2]. Multimedia courses, such as for example in i-school, are the basis of distance education and form the basis of educational and methodological kits.

We will analyze the educational and methodological package using the example of the Russian Law Academy of the Ministry of Justice of the Russian Federation. The electronic educational and methodical complex or EUMK in the distance learning system of the Academy has the following structure:

Methodical section:

information about the author;

educational and methodological recommendations and instructions to the student, including the target setting and requirements for the level of mastering the program and forms of intermediate control;

the content of the academic discipline or the course program;

approximate topics of coursework, control (according to the curriculum) and theses;

bibliographic list;

legal acts;

questions for intermediate certification;

educational and thematic plan of the discipline.

Didactic section:

lecture material on all topics of the course, questions for self-control and preparation for testing on each topic, tests on all topics;

glossary;

schemes, drawings, tables, examples of problem solving;

task for control work (according to the curriculum)

Control and measuring section:

Intermediate assessment test (credit or curriculum exam)

System of consultations and communication between teacher and student

The sequence of studying the lecture course and passing the current control is determined by the educational and thematic plan [2].

Uzbek educational institutions have accumulated significant experience in creating electronic educational tools, in developing informative and educational websites, and in introducing information technologies into the educational process. However, this activity is fragmented and fragmentary and requires the organization of systematic work on the collection, classification and placement of information, educational and methodological and additional materials in a single information space.

The use of Internet technologies imposes new requirements on the educational and methodological support of educational programs (primarily, teacher training programs). How to design educational programs, how to conduct a lesson using Internet technologies and the question that is of paramount importance in this work.

Bibliography:

1. Voronina T.P., Kashitsyn V.P., Molchanova O.P. Education in the era of new information technologies. - M.: Publishing house "Informatik", 1995. - 220 p.

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2. Vymyatnin V.M. Information and technological support of DO // Bulletin of the Association "Open University of Western Siberia". Issue 1. Barnaul, 1999. S. 16-29.

3. Demkin V.P., Mozhaeva G.V. Educational and methodological support of educational programs based on information technology // Open and distance education. - 2003. - N2 (10). - S. 5 - 8.

Electronic learning resources

1. <http://www.lib.socio.msu.ru>

2. <http://www.socioline.ru>

3. <http://www.socio.rin.ru>